

New Eyes in the Deep – the rise of marine autonomous systems for civil and defence purposes, and a brief look at laws and regulations that apply to their use.

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Synopsis

Marine autonomous systems, be they underwater or surface vehicles are growing in numbers, maturing as technologies used by civil, science and military operators, and are gaining new capabilities. It is possible to insure autonomous systems at a reasonable rate. The regulatory frameworks pertaining to their use vary from country to country, but the international law for armed marine autonomous systems is out of date and would benefit from revision and update.

This paper is a light-touch review of typical uses and capabilities of systems, does not contain classified or commercial in confidence material, based on the author's 25+ years of familiarity with marine autonomous systems as they have evolved from laboratory prototypes into routinely used platforms for science, survey and surveillance.

Keywords— Robotics, Autonomy, security, policy, regulation

1. Introduction

Marine autonomous systems have been used for centuries for data transfer and military purposes. A 'message in a bottle' or the simple 'St Kilda Mailboat' - a small wooden boat attached to an inflated sheep's bladder used to transmit messages from an isolated island to the shore of the mainland – were effective, if very low-bandwidth methods of delivering information across the sea. The use of fireships, unmanned vessels set alight to drift into an enemy's fleet or harbour, goes back to the time of the ancient Greeks, and were used effectively by Drake against the Spanish Armada. In more recent

times the naval mine, and torpedoes launched from ships or submarines have demonstrated that marine autonomous systems are weapons able to deny sea space to opponents, and to directly engage their vessels, even capital ships.

Fast forward to the 21st century and the new generation of robotic systems are maturing quickly, no longer creatures of the laboratory, but of proven capability, increasing reliability, and possessing an ever-growing range of mission capabilities. Within a decade or two at most, they will have transformed some aspects of naval operations, particularly as platforms able to deny access to sea-space, as they already are changing how civilian scientific and commercial operators gather data at sea.

2. Types of marine autonomous system (MAS)

Marine autonomous systems – hereafter MAS – fall broadly into the autonomous surface vehicle (ASV) and autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) category, but this is already becoming blurred as some new models operate in either mode, and a handful of designs are capable of flight, enabling fast transit to the operations area before landing on the sea, then diving to carry out the mission. Most systems are intended to be re-used after recovery, recharging and data download, though some military devices are designed for a single mission, especially if they carry a weapon – the most powerfully-armed known example being the Russian nuclear powered 'Poseidon' (NATO 'Kanyon') AUV with a thermonuclear warhead

reported as in the tens of megatons range, and possibly 'salted' with Cobalt 60.

Vehicles further sub-divide into those that are self-propelled, and those that drift along on the surface or submerged. Finally, there are autonomous systems that are capable of self-deployment, but once on station they remain stationary either as surface or seabed-based systems.

Excluding military systems, the earliest large-scale adopters, and developers, of modern MAS have been the international community of oceanographers at marine science institutions such as Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute in the USA and National Oceanography Centre in UK. For oceanographers, the driver for development and use of MAS is the requirement for sustained ocean observations in all seasons, and in near-real-time. The global supply of oceanographic research ships is limited, and satellite data only tells observers data about the sea surface, with a limited additional amount of data apparent from measures of gravitational fields and radar altimetry. To learn about even the most basic criteria such as water temperature, sub-surface currents and salinity you need sensors that can penetrate the surface layer, and ideally get below the thermocline and start exploring deep ocean waters. Without access to this data the accuracy of weather & climate forecasts, the ability to give early warning of hurricanes, El Nino events, and other high-impact phenomena falls off rapidly, as the ocean stores most of the heat energy of the ocean-atmosphere, including over 90% of the additional heat estimated to have been generated as a consequence of post-industrialisation global warming.

The most basic type of MAS are free-floating drifters, either wind & current-driven on the surface, or able to profile the top few hundred metres of the water column, and relay data to base via satellite when they return to the surface. The technology of neutrally-buoyant floats was developed in the 1960s, 70s, & 80s and led eventually to the international 'Argo' programme that uses advanced profiling floats able to vary their buoyancy, sink to a pre-determined depth, then surface after a few weeks to transmit data before submerging again. Since 2000 the network of Argo floats has grown to the point where as of 14th August 2019 there were 3846 Argo floats in active service, see

http://www.argo.ucsd.edu/About_Argo.html for latest status and technical information. To comply with international conventions (in particular Part XIII of UNCLOS) most science floats are deliberately limited in the technology that they carry, as float operators prefer to avoid needing to seek diplomatic clearance for marine scientific research every time a float enters the waters of another country – the floats cannot be steered. They are also not well suited to shallow-water operations as they can become grounded in soft sediments over continental shelves, and apart from a small number of specialist ultra-deep versions rated to 6000m or more, are limited to depths of around 2000m.

Next up the list on terms of capability, and very closely technically related to the 'Argo' floats, are profiling gliders. These are effectively floats lying horizontally, using similar buoyancy variation and the addition of wings, to carry out long range oceanographic missions gliding on density surfaces. Like floats, they surface periodically to update position and transmit data, but they can be instructed to set a general course, or to enter a sustained spiralling profile mode (a 'virtual mooring') to provide data from a reasonably fixed position. Gliders are becoming tools of choice for marine science users, as they can stay at sea for extended periods of months at a time, are capable of recovery and re-use, can carry an extended package of science instrumentation and have the ability to constrain their area of operations allowing avoidance of maritime borders. In military trials, gliders have demonstrated the ability to detect submerged submarines through passive acoustic means, but they do not have the speed or on-board power to track a submerged submarine. Some gliders are fitted with small auxiliary power units to enable them to transit to an area of interest more quickly, or maintain position against a current, but these are low power units, not intended for sustained sprints.

Floats and gliders fulfil science roles sub-surface, but a fast-growing market is that for autonomous surface vehicles. As with floats, the simplest designs simply drift. In most instances there is a degree of propulsion and navigational freedom using a mixture of motors, foils, and sails to enable the vehicle to transit to a desired location, and then enter low-power mode to carry out observations or

surveillance. ASVs come in shapes and sizes ranging from less than a metre through to tens of metres length, with the larger vessels effectively remote-controlled ships rather than fully autonomous systems. A recent development is the use of ASVs as a communications hub paired with a swarm of submerged vehicles, or as a mother-ship able to retrieve and refuel the daughter vessels. Typical uses are offshore survey, monitoring and surveillance – for example providing fisheries patrol services, patrolling marine protected areas, identifying local shipping, acting as data relays, and taking surface observations of weather & oceanographic parameters.

As we move up the complexity and cost chain, autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) that are more sophisticated than floats and gliders now exist in a wide variety of configurations.

In the early 1990s a handful of pioneering companies & institutions were beginning to produce autonomous vehicles able to carry useful payloads for extended duration missions. The first notable success was the Theseus AUV built by International Submarine Engineering, designed around a specific requirement to lay fibre-optic cable under ice off the Arctic coast of Canada. See [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Theseus_\(AUV\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Theseus_(AUV)) The Theseus missions demonstrated that an AUV could be used for sustained under ice operations, and that reliable navigation was possible using inertial navigation systems and upwards/downwards looking sonars able to read the vehicle's track relative to the seabed or under ice.

Shortly after Theseus the UK's National Oceanography Centre began trials of the 'Autosub' AUV, designed from the outset as a long-range autonomous vehicle for hydrographic survey and oceanographic research. The original Autosub Mk1 used primary cells rather than rechargeable units but could travel for over 1000km and submerge to 1600m. After two decades of experience the current 'Autosub Long Range' vehicle is more compact than the original, enabling launch and recovery from a wider range of mother ships or shore launch, and can dive to 6000m, and stay at sea for periods of weeks or months at a time. Like many other AUVs, the early Autosub concepts included defence-related roles such as detection and tracking of submarines, but the end of the Cold War shut down that line of funding and

throughout the 90s and early 2000s the bulk of investment in successful AUV design came from the offshore survey sector, seeking ways to use AUVs to carry out seabed survey and mapping. Kongsberg's 'Hugin' series of large AUVs quickly established a market lead in the survey sector, and today the Hugin family of vehicles are specified in a range of depth capabilities and sensor configurations, so that they can be used for scientific, industrial and defence applications - see <https://www.kongsberg.com/maritime/products/marine-robotics/autonomous-underwater-vehicles/AUV-hugin/>

3. The State of the Art

The most recent commercial AUVs combine the role of robot explorer with that of a remotely operated vehicle and can transition between autonomous and remote-control mode, obtaining battery recharge from seabed-placed inductive charging stations and uploading data by seabed connector, short range blue laser and acoustic means. An excellent example is the 2019 'Freedom' hybrid AUV/ROV from Oceaneering, which builds on knowledge gained in defence sector as well as commercial and scientific work – see

<https://www.oceaneering.com/brochures/freedom-rov/> The 'Freedom' system has a maximum depth rating of 6000m and is designed to spend most of its working life underwater, only returning to mother ship or shore when deep maintenance is required.

Other innovative designs include the UltraDeep Explorer from Alseamar of France, combining glider and self-propelled AUV technology, rated to 6000m and optimised for the deep sea mining industry – see <https://www.alseamar-alcen.com/alseamar/company>

The original Autosub has upgraded into a family of highly capable surveillance and science AUVs, offering very long endurance and high payload, see <https://noc.ac.uk/facilities/marine-autonomous-robotic-systems/autosubs>. At the smaller end of the scale are hand-carried robots such as the EcoSub <https://www.ecosub.uk> suitable for single deployments in response to oil spills or to carry out other kinds of mission for civil or defence purposes.

Small AUVs for military purposes are evolving quickly, with innovative designs such as the SHARD from Australia's DefendTEX mimicking a squid or jellyfish to be even harder to detect and evade

— see
<https://www.businessinsider.com/video-squid-military-drone-is-sea-mine-2019-9>

4. Current typical Missions

Most civilian use of MAS to date has been by the science and research sector, closely followed by offshore survey for industry. For scientists, the high daily cost of using research ships greatly constrains the number of sea days available for deployment of sensors & instruments, particularly in winter months, remote locations or under ice. Adding autonomous systems, even the simplest types, greatly increases the spatial coverage of data gathering, complementing that provided by remote sensing satellites (which are effective, but generally unable to retrieve much useful data about conditions beneath the sea surface), and enables data to be gathered all year, and from locations that are difficult or expensive to access in other ways. For example, sustained under-ice missions are all but impossible for civilian researchers to carry out without access to AUVs – military platforms are sometimes made available, but there are constraints on where manned submarines can safely travel, and they cannot dive very deep compared with robotic vehicles, and treaties prevent nuclear-powered submarines from being available for Antarctic work.

Science AUVs and surface systems are used for oceanography, fisheries research, water sampling, seabed mapping, photography and video work, exploration of caves, mid-ocean ridges and under-ice, work in winter storms and hurricanes, coral reef inspection, data relay and will in future be the platforms of choice for exploring the seas and oceans of the moons Europa, Enceladus and Titan. Commercial sector AUVs can carry out the same roles as the science/research community but most are deployed for mapping the seafloor; high resolution survey of offshore infrastructure, ports and harbour installations; pipeline inspections; spill/leakage detection and specialist roles such as searching for downed aircraft and ships. In the future, fully autonomous mining machines may carry out the bulk of deep ocean extraction of metal

ores and rare earths, for later collection by recovery ships.

Military AUVs carry out many of the same tasks as the science & industry users, but with the added categories of stealthy surveillance, patrol and mapping, and in some instances, they can be armed and used for defensive or offensive purposes. Early adopters found that AUVs were well-suited for mine countermeasures work such as mapping mine fields, and they make excellent platforms for active or passive sonar systems. Low speed can constrain their use as anti-submarine warfare platforms, but this is changing as a new generation of high-specification robots become available that can travel at speed to transit to a search area, then shift to slow, silent stealth mode while hunting.

Russia's controversial 'Kanyon' AUV is a nuclear powered and armed system presumably intended as a second-strike strategic nuclear weapon (the warhead is reputedly in the multi-megaton class) as it is too slow for first strike, but ideal for retaliation purposes – it can be launched from 'bastion' areas in Russian coastal waters or under ice, travels slow and deep for weeks, then can make a high-speed dash into coastal waters aimed at seaports, harbours, defence installation and cities. With a very high yield warhead bursting in shallow waters, vast areas of land would be inundated by a highly radioactive mix of seawater, sand and shingle blasted from the seabed and deposited over the coastal zone, rendering the target area uninhabitable for an extended period, particularly if, as has been claimed, the warhead is 'salted' with cobalt 60 to increase long-term lethality. 'Kanyon' would be very hard to detect and counter except during the final few minutes of approach to the target area. Russian sources have claimed that it is 'supercavitating' and capable of over 100 knots, but the hull form shown in press releases does not suggest supercavitation capability, limiting speed to 60 knots at most. Perhaps there is more than one version of 'Kanyon', and a high-speed variant has not yet been shown to Western audiences. One reputable OSINT writer ('Strikepod systems', August 2019) has speculated that the number of Kanyons known to be on order, 32, is similar to the total number of western SSBNs that could conceivably be ranged against the Russia, and he argues that system could be intended to act as a 'tail' for enemy SSBNs, to be detonated in a time

of conflict to wipe out the SSBN fleet. It's an possibility, but in the real world it is very unlikely that SSBNs could be so easily found and tagged – unless 'Kanyon' systems were pre-deployed right outside naval bases, waiting for their prey to leave the harbour.

5. Law & Insurance

The Law of the Sea has evolved over the centuries into the systems now in common use across the global ocean, in particular the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea, which governs most aspects of the delimitation of maritime borders, freedom of navigation, rights of 'innocent passage' and so on. There are also conventions such as the International Convention on the Safety of Life at Sea 1974 (SOLAS) that govern safe operation of merchant shipping. Within the UK, the marine planning and licensing system administered by the Marine Management Organisation has classified autonomous systems as 'vessels' so that they enjoy similar freedom of navigation rights to ships with crew, and don't require a license to carry out their duties unless that are physically interfering with the seabed, installing and removing structures or discharging chemicals into the marine environment. Most operators liaise with the civil and military authorities to ensure that a 'Notice to Mariners' for the relevant geographical area is issued while fully autonomous operations are underway, to ensure safety of shipping, user conflict avoidance, and alert seafarers to the likelihood that they might observe marine autonomous systems at rest or underway on the surface, and not to attempt to 'salvage' or otherwise recover systems which are unattended and carrying out work. This occurred several times in the early years of autonomous operations, for example with fishermen hauling vehicles on board then asking for a reward for recovering a 'lost' vehicle. This led, at least in the case of civilian systems, to the adoption of various lights, stripes and markings on vehicles to warn that they did not require any form of 'rescue'! Other countries will have their own preferred systems, there not yet being a common standard in place globally. Insurance cover for autonomous systems has been available from specialist brokers at Lloyds of London and other locations since the late 1990s, and risks of loss are increasingly well understood,

so that reasonable rates are available for commercial users.

The use of intelligent, self-steering, armed marine autonomous systems was not envisaged when the laws pertaining to unmanned systems were first drafted, with the Hague Convention Part 8 'Laws of War - Laying of Automatic Submarine Contact Mines' of October 1907 (see https://avalon.law.yale.edu/20th_century/hague08.asp) perhaps the last time this technology was seriously explored.

The UN system is concerned about the increasing autonomy of weapons systems, and the algorithms used to make firing decisions, and these concerns are being addressed via the UN Institute for Disarmament Research (UNIDR) with their meetings being attended by the UK's Royal Navy and Foreign & Commonwealth Office – see for example

<http://www.unidir.org/publications/security-and-technology> with link to <http://www.unidir.org/programmes/security-and-technology/the-weaponization-of-increasingly-autonomous-technologies-phase-iii> The annual San Remo Round Table, hosted by the International Institute of Humanitarian Law and the International Committee of the Red Cross (see <http://iihl.org/sanremo-round-table-3/>) raises new developments in technology as they apply to armed conflict, see the San Remo Manual on International Law Applicable to Armed Conflicts at Sea, 12 June 1994 (see <https://www.legal-tools.org/doc/118957/pdf/>)

6. Conclusion

Marine Autonomous Systems, in all of their guises, are no longer novel or prototype machines. Hundreds of units (thousands if you include profiling floats) are in use, confidence in their capability and the likelihood or otherwise of safe retrieval at the end of a mission is well understood, and a new generation of armed systems are becoming available. However, the legal frameworks in which systems operate have, for the most part, not been updated, and laws written for armed systems are based on technologies such as sea mines and torpedoes.

The time is right for the community of users of marine autonomous systems to reach international agreement on new regulatory approaches to

systems which will continue to improve, increase their levels of built-in intelligence, and grow their capabilities to challenge the dominance of crewed systems at sea, be it for civilian or military purposes. Learned Societies & Professional Bodies such as IMarEST, the Society for Underwater Technology and Marine Technology Society all have a role to play in updating the legislation and ensuring that marine autonomous systems are effective, safe and reliable technologies.

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